

MISSIONS TO THE SURFACE AND THE SUBSURFACE OF THE MOON: THE UNIVERSITY OF VIGO'S CONTRIBUTION

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Introduction:

The exploration of the moon has emerged as a priority for space agencies, driven by the scientific and strategic significance of lunar missions. The surface and the subsurface through lava caves are both the main targets for those missions. Beyond its enigmatic beauty, the Moon serves as a unique celestial laboratory, offering insights into the early history of our solar system and Earth itself. Understanding the geology, composition, and dynamics of the lunar surface and caves not only sheds light on fundamental questions about planetary formation and evolution but also holds practical implications for future space exploration endeavors. Furthermore, the Moon represents a potential stepping stone for humanity's expansion into the cosmos, serving as a testing ground for technologies and habitats crucial for sustained human presence in space.

Studying the lunar south pole presents a captivating frontier for scientific inquiry and exploration. This region of the Moon is shrouded in perpetual darkness within its deep polar craters, where the potential presence of water ice has garnered significant interest, not only for understanding of the Moon's volatile history and geology but also holds profound implications for future lunar exploration and even human settlement. In the pursuit of establishing sustainable lunar habitats, the lava caves are potential candidates to be explored, as they provide protection from radiation and meteorite bombardment, as well as stable thermal conditions and easy access to resources. They are unique geological formations that are created as a result of cooling basaltic lava flows.

To develop in-situ exploration, rovers play a crucial role, providing the necessary mobility to navigate and conduct experiments across the lunar terrain. Moreover, an extended rover-crane system can also provide the needed access, power and communications to small rovers for operating inside lava caves.

The European Space Agency (ESA) launched several campaigns through the Open Space Innovation Platform and through open tenders to select european consortia for studying different systems of exploring the south pole and lunar caves. University of Vigo has participated in three of those projects in the last three years: RoboCrane, Antennas for Underground Communication, and AMPERS.

RoboCrane:

RoboCrane is a project that addresses the challenges of exploring lava caves, specifically a) the access to the interior of the cave through the steep entrance (50 m of vertical pit with unstable rims); b) the lack of solar light inside them and c) the lack of a direct line of sight for communications with the surface. The project proposes a crane to deploy a Charging Head (CH) at the bottom of a skylight, vertical pit that connects lava tubes and the lunar surface. This CH acts as a battery charger and communication relay for the exploring robots. The crane also helps to overcome the unstable terrain around the skylight rim and can be used to deploy the exploring robots, simplifying their design constraints and mass budget. The design of RoboCrane has been implemented in a parametric tool to allow for adjustments based on changing input variables [1], and was selected, along with another project, to move forward to the next stage of development through the Concurrent Design Facility study.

The primary objective of the mission is to explore the Moon's pyroclastic deposits, with a focus on the Marius Hill skylight located at 14.091°N, 303.223°E. The mission is planned to last for the 14 days of a synodic lunar period, during which the surface around the target cave will be exposed to sunlight. The system is expected to be capable of traveling an estimated 500 meters distance from the landing point to the skylight's edge. It must also adhere to the physical limitations imposed by launch and transportation systems, such as the European Large Logistics Lander (EL3). Uvigo contribution was focused on the system engineering study, and on the thermal control design during the CDF study. Its concept of operations is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Concept of operations of RoboCrane.

Antennae for underground communication:

In the pursuit of establishing sustainable lunar habitats, the exigency for innovative communication

systems tailored to the unique challenges presented by subterranean lunar caves becomes increasingly evident. In lunar cave entrances, access points need to be established, to communicate the lava tube with the Moon surface. Several strategies are identified to provide communications further inside up to 200 m, as mobile ad-hoc robots network with bounded relaying, but an efficient coordination between robots shall be achieved. The wireless mesh network can be support with the 802.11s protocol.

Uvigo team is involved in the structural and thermal analysis and tests of the proposed prototypes of antennas during the project. We also have developed simulations on the communication channels considering several parameters of the cave walls, ground, and floor, the height of the antenna, the distances reached, or the power received.

Figure 2. Communication channel and antenna structural analyses.

AMPERS:

One of the key challenges faced by lunar rovers is the dynamic thermal environment, fluctuating between extreme temperatures from day to night and transitioning between illuminated and shaded regions. The efficient operation of the Electrical Power Subsystem (EPS) is critical for the success of lunar rovers, making it imperative to address the complexities of thermal management. This study belongs to a project funded by ESA called “Power management conditioning for hybrid radioisotope-solar power systems”. The Uvigo’s work focuses on the conceptual design considerations and thermal control strategies for a hybrid EPS, incorporating solar panels, batteries, and a Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generator (RTG). This hybrid configuration ensures a reliable and continuous power supply to the rover under diverse lunar scenarios. The research emphasizes the significance of thermal analysis and control design in the sizing of a lunar rover and its EPS. The study focuses on a rover intended for operations at the moon’s South Pole, where unique cold environmental conditions pose specific challenges. Thermal analyses are conducted in ESATAN, enabling a geometric representation of the lunar environment and the

rover. Subsequently, two models are developed in Python and EcoSimpro to examine the static and dynamic thermo-electric behavior of the hybrid EPS. The findings presented in this work offer valuable insights for the development of future lunar rovers by ESA, providing a foundation for the advancement of space exploration missions in the quest for a deeper understanding of our celestial neighbor.

Ejemplo de pie de figura (Fuente: NASA/JPL)

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